

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

О'TKIR HOSHIMOVNING "DUNYONING ISHLARI" QISSASI VA UNING INGLIZ TILIDAGI "AFFAIRS OF LIFE" TARJIMASIDA MILLIY MADANIYATNING SAQLANISHI.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tilshunoslik sohasida keng o'rganilayotgan mavzu korpus tilshunosligi, xususan parallel korpus prizmasi tahlilida asl va tarjima matnlar o'rtasida asliyat muammosining tadqiqi haqida so'z yuritilgan. Xususan, o'zbek yozuvchisi O'tkir Hoshimovning mashhur asarlaridan biri bo'lmish "Dunyoning ishlari" va uning Obidxon Mo'minov tomonidan qilingan tarjimasida "Affairs of life" asarlari tarjimasida misollar ko'rib chiqilgan

Kalit so'zlar: korpus tilshunosligi, korpus, parallel korpus, asl matn, tarjima matn, asliyat, lingvokulturologik so'zlar.

СОХРАНЕНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ В РАССКАЗЕ ОТКИРА ГАШИМОВА «ДЕЛА ЖИЗНИ» И ЕГО ПЕРЕВОДЕ «ДЕЛА ЖИЗНИ» НА АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫК.

АННОТАЦИЯ.

В данной статье речь идет о корпусной лингвистике, широко изучаемой теме в области лингвистики, в частности, исследовании проблемы аутентичности оригинальных и переведенных текстов в параллельном корпусно-призматическом анализе. В частности, были рассмотрены примеры перевода одного из известных произведений узбекского писателя Откира Гашимова «Дела мира» и его перевода Обидхана Моминова «Дела жизни».

Ключевые слова: корпусная лингвистика, корпус, параллельный корпус, оригинальный текст, переведенный текст, оригинальность, лингвокультурные слова.

PRESERVATION OF NATIONAL CULTURE IN OTKIR HASHIMOV'S STORY "AFFAIRS OF LIFE" AND HIS TRANSLATION "AFFAIRS OF LIFE" IN ENGLISH.

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

Abstract. This article deals with corpus linguistics, a widely studied topic in the field of linguistics, in particular, the research of the problem of authenticity between original and translated texts in parallel corpus prism analysis. In particular, examples of the translation of one of the famous works of the Uzbek writer O'tkir Hashimov, and its translation by Obidkhan Mominov, "Affairs of life" were considered.

Key words: corpus linguistics, corpus, parallel corpus, original text, translated text, originality, linguocultural words.

“Dunyoning ishlari” — O‘zbekiston xalq yozuvchisi O‘tkir Hoshimov qalamiga mansub memuar qissa. Asar katta-kichik hikoyalardan iborat, uzoq yillar davomida yozilgan va to‘liq tarzda 2005-yilda *"Sharq nashriyoti"* tomonidan nashr etilgan. Keyinchalik boshqa nashriyotlar tomonidan ham ko‘p bora qayta nashr etildi.

Kitobning orqa tomonida adibning quyidagi so‘zlari keltirilgan: *"Dunyoda hech bir chegarani tan olmaydigan va quyosh kabi muttasil nur sohib turadigan sehri kuch bor. Bu—Ona mehri! Alloh Onani shunday yaratgan!"*

Uning qirقدan ortiq asarlari ming-minglab kitobxonlarning ma‘naviy mulkiga aylanishga ulgurgan. Asarlari oddiy va xalqchilligi bilan ajralib turadi. "Dunyoning ishlari" asari ham ana shunday xalqchil asarlar sirasiga kiradi. Adib o‘z asarini 2005-yilgi nashrida shunday ta‘riflagan: " Bu qissa katta-kichik novellalardan iborat. Biroq, ularning barchasida eng aziz odam-Onam siymosi bor. Bunday odamlarning hammasini o‘z ko‘zim bilan ko‘rganman. Faqat, ba’zilarining ismi o‘zgardi, xolos. Bu odamlarning qismati ham qaysidir jihatdan onamga bog‘langan". Adib bu asariga o‘zining barcha samimiy hislarini tarannum etgan, samimiyat urug‘ini kitobxon diliga sochgan. O‘tkir

Hoshimovning asarlarida yetakchilik qilgan insoniylik tarannumi butun insoniyat uchun hayotiy saboq bo‘ladi.¹

O‘zbekiston xalq yozuvchisi Said Ahmad qissani shunday tariflagan: *"Dunyoning ishlari asarini qissa emas, doston deb atashni istardim. U qo‘shiqday o‘qiladi. Uni o‘qib turib, o‘z onalarimizni o‘ylab ketamiz. Shu mushfiq, shu jafokash onalarimiz oldidagi bir umr uzib bo‘lmas qarzarimizning aqalli*

¹ <https://hp.jdpu.uz/index.php/hp/article/view/2554/1702>

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

*bittasini uza oldikmi, degan bir andisha, bir savol ko‘z oldimizda ko‘ndalang turib oladi. Qissa bizni insofga, insonni qadrlashga, hurmat qilishga chaqiradi*²

“Ermon buvaning tilagi” deb nomlangan hikoyada asliyatdagi matn va uning ingliz tilidagi tarjimasida asliyatni anglatuvchi fikrlar qay tarzda ingliz tiliga o‘girilganini qarab chiqamiz.

Asl matnda “*Xullas, nima bo‘lgandayam u oqsoqlanib yuradi. Bahor paytlari ola sigirini yetaklab kelib qoladi. Qo‘lida hassa, sigirining butun shoxiga tuguncha ilib qo‘yilgan. O‘tloqqa yetganidan keyin sigirning shoxidagi tugunchani oladi-da, o‘zini qo‘yib yuboradi. Belidagi qiyiqchasini tol soyasiga tashlab «bismillohu rahmonur rahim» deb maysa ustiga yonboshlaydi. Ola sigir shundayqina uning yonida poyezdek pishillab o‘tlashga tushadi. Ora-chora shu ishim ma‘qulmi, degandek egasiga qarab-qarab qo‘yadi.*”³ parchasi ingliz tiliga:

“And so whatever might have happened he limped. He came leading his variegated cow during the spring. There was a stick in his hand and he hung a bundle on his cow’s unbroken horn. When they reached the field, he took the bundle and set the cow free. He put his belt under the willow and lied on the grass saying “In the name of Allah”. Variegated cow herded near him. From time to time it looked at its owner as if it asked permission from him.”⁴ deb tarjima qilingan.

Yuqorida berilgan parchada “***Belidagi qiyiqchasini tol soyasiga tashlab «bismillohu rahmonur rahim» deb maysa ustiga yonboshlaydi.***” iborasiga e‘tibor qaratmoqchimiz. Bilamizki o‘zbekchilikda har bir ishni boshlashdan oldin “Bismilloh” bilan boshlaymiz, bu bizning millatimizga va asliyatimizga singib ketgan, qon tomirimizgacha o‘rnashgan tushuncha hisoblanadi. Va bu tushuncha boshqa millat vakillari uchun yot bo‘lganligi sababli, boshqa xalqlarda bu kabi so‘zlar nutqda uchramasligi sababli tarjimon berilgan bu gapni “***He put his belt under the willow and lied on the grass saying “In the name of Allah”.***” tarzida kitobxonga yetkazishga harakat qilgan.

Shu hikoya davomida berilgan keyingi parchada:

Asl matnda: “*Assalomu alaykum, buvajon, – deb salom beradi. – Vaalaykum assalom, mullo bo‘ling, tasadduq, – deydi Ermon buva salmoqlab. Baribir uning ovozi salmoqli chiqmaydi: xotinlarnikidek ingichka, ammo nihoyatda mehribon*”⁵.

² https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dunyoning_ishlari#cite_note-3

³ Hoshimov O. Dunyoning ishlari: qissa. – Toshkent: “Sharq” nashriyot-matbaa aksiyadorlik kompaniyasi bosh tahririyati, 2005. – B. 66

⁴ Utkir Hoshimov. Affairs of life. Stories (Translator: O.M.Muminov). – Tashkent, 2013. – P.45

⁵ Hoshimov O. Dunyoning ishlari: qissa. – Toshkent: “Sharq” nashriyot-matbaa aksiyadorlik kompaniyasi bosh tahririyati, 2005.

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

Tarjimada: “– *Good morning, dear grandfather, – he greeted him.*

– *Good morning, well done, – answers grandfather Ermon weighty. His voice shouted kindly as a woman but very kindly.*”⁶ deb ingliz kitobxonlariga yetkazilgan. Yuqorida berilgan misralarga e’tibor qaratadigan bo’lsak azaldan o’zbek xalqining bolajonligi, farzandlariga nisbatan juda mehribon va chiroyli tilda gaplashilishi haqida ortiqcha izohga hojat qolmasa kerak. Yozuvchi tomonidan yozilgan “*Vaalaykum assalom, mullo bo’ling, tasadduq,*” degan jumlar ingliz tiliga “*Good morning, well done, – answers grandfather Ermon weighty*” deb oddiygina tarjima qilinganidan shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, bu kabi muomala madaniyati bizning millatimiz aslyatiga xos bo’lib, uni tarjima qilganda bu so’zlarni to’laqonli ifodalab beradigan jumlar mos kelmagan.

Qissada keltirilgan “Ermon buvaning tilagi” hikoyasini mutolaa qilishda davom ettiradigan bo’lsak,

O’tkir Hoshimov qalamiga mansub bo’lgan “Dunyoning ishlari” qissasidan olingan “Ermon buvaning tilagi” hikoyasini o’zbek va ingliz tiliga tarjima qilingan matnlarini jadval ko’rinishida berib, unda asl matndan ingliz tiliga tarjima qilinganda aslyatning saqlanib qolishi haqidagi savollarga misollar yordamida atroflicha javob topishga harakat qildik. Bunda berilgan misollardan shuni anglashimiz mumkinki, asl matn yozilgan xalqning milliylikini, qadriyatlarini boshqa tilga o’girganda tarjimondan juda yuksak mahorat talab qilinadi.

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⁶ Utkir Hoshimov. Affairs of life. Stories (Translator: O.M.Muminov). – Tashkent, 2013. – P.45

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

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